

BARELY VISIBLE DAMAGE THRESHOLD IN GRAPHITE EPOXY
E. Demuts, R.S. Sandhu and G.E. Maddux
Flight Dynamics Directorate, Wright Laboratory
Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio 45433-6553

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses results of low velocity impact tests. These tests, as a goal, were designed to correspond to the current USAF damage tolerance criteria for advanced composite airframes. Impactor velocity, impact energy, dent depths and damaged areas associated with these tests are presented for AS4/3501-6 graphite epoxy. The flat and rectangular 17.78 cm by 25.40 cm specimens had five thicknesses of 9, 26, 48, 74 and 96 plies and an ambient moisture content. Specimens were impacted in their center while being clamped between two plates each having a 12.7 cm square central opening. Extents of manufacturing flaws and impact damage were obtained by an ultrasonic nondestructive inspection method. Dent depths were determined by the shadow Moire technique. Experimental data of the nine-ply specimens (1.200 mm thick) suggest that for laminates thinner than 2.54 mm the dent depth for initial damage assumption purposes (currently specified by the USAF as 2.54 mm) should be limited to the laminate thickness to avoid a through-penetration and a damage area that is related to ballistic rather than low velocity impact. Test data from specimens thicker than nine plies reasonably fall within the expected ranges. In general, obtained data tend to supplement and expand the currently available damage tolerance data base for composite materials and structures.

KEYWORDS: Damage tolerance; Low velocity impact; Barely visible damage; Graphite epoxy; Experimental data.

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural integrity requirements of airframes have the purpose to assure the aircraft owners and users that the airframe would possess a desired degree of static strength, stiffness, durability (fatigue life) and safety (damage tolerance). This general idea applies to airframes fabricated from any combination of various materials. With the advent of advanced composites, such as graphite fiber reinforced epoxies, bismaleimides (BMI's), polyetheretherketone (PEEK) or other thermoset or thermoplastic resins, whose behavior is vastly different from that of metals, the development of appropriate structural integrity requirements was a definite necessity.

One of the greatest concerns by the composites community is the so called barely visible damage (BVD). Such damage may be caused, for example, by dropping objects, such as tools or tool boxes, on the structure, by kicking or dropping a structural panel or by runway debris thrown on the airframe by landing gear tires. Since the definition of "barely visible" depends on a person's eyesight as well as the available lighting conditions and the location of the damage, it becomes a subjective matter. The U.S. Air Force, for instance, defines BVD in a composite as a damage caused by a 25.4-inch diameter hemispherical steel impactor travelling at 4.88 m/sec resulting in a 2.54 mm deep dent.

It has been found in a U.S. Air Force sponsored damage tolerance program that a BVD, as defined above, may reduce the original strength of the structure at the BVD location by as much as 60%. To preclude a potential catastrophic failure due to such damage, the damage tolerance requirements compel the designer to (1) assume that a damage of given proportions exist and (2) to provide enough material so that the resulting structure is capable of withstanding all service conditions in the presence of the assumed damage without failure. Since the proportions of the assumable initial damage are prescribed in the damage tolerance requirements are arbitrary discretions of the aircraft owners or users, the subjective nature of providing safety is extended beyond

just the definition of BVD. Although arbitrary, the requirements generally are based on a sound rationale.

Usually, the design of the thinner damage tolerant composite laminates is governed by the BVD. But as thicknesses of the laminates increase, to produce an impact-caused BVD, no matter how defined, an impact of unreasonably high magnitude may be required. To maintain the damage tolerance requirements reasonable and realistic, the design of the thicker composite laminates is not governed by assuming that the initial damage is the BVD but by assuming the existence of a damage caused by an impact of a prescribed magnitude usually smaller than that required to produce 2.54 mm deep dent. For example, the U.S. Air Force currently requires that the assumed initial damage be either the BVD, as previously defined, or that damage caused by a 136 joules impact at 4.88 m/sec, whichever damage is less (Ref 1).

2. OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

This paper will discuss some procedures and observations of an in-house experimental investigation of damage tolerance in advanced composites. The overall objective of this investigation is to determine (1) the impact energy associated with barely visible damage (BVD), as defined by the Air Force, due to low velocity impact in those composite laminates whose damage tolerant design is governed by the BVD and (2) the extent of damage resulting from the low velocity impact in laminates whose damage tolerant design is governed by either the BVD or a 136 joule impact. Although the complete investigation included three advanced composite material systems (graphite fiber reinforced epoxy, bismaleimide and thermoplastic) the presentations of this paper will cover only the results pertaining to the AS4/3501-6 graphite epoxy.

In addition, this paper will present the following: description of the test plan, selection of the layup, thicknesses and stacking sequences of the specimens, fabrication of panels and cutting them into specimens, pre-impact inspection of specimens, the specific test equipment

for introducing impact damage, the test procedures, including trial or calibration tests, post-impact inspection of test specimens for determining impact dent depths and damaged areas, discussion of test results and conclusions based on the test observations.

3. TEST PLAN

3.1 Specimens One of the concerns in designing a test involving composite laminates is the selection of the layup for the test specimens. A layup in fiber-reinforced composites is known as the apportionment of various ply orientations in a laminate. Although, theoretically, there could be an infinite number of ply orientation combinations, the most versatile, and hence popular, is the 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° family producing a laminate that consists of certain percentage of each of the three ply orientations. For the purposes of the investigation reported in this paper, only one nominal layup was selected for the low velocity impact tests - 10% of 0° , 80% of $\pm 45^\circ$ and 10% of 90° fiber orientations. Because of the relatively high percentage of $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, the selected layup (10/80/10) is considered as "soft" in comparison with, say, all 0° unidirectional layup which is considered as "hard". The "soft" layup, because of its higher strain to failure, improves damage tolerance at the expense of lower strength in the 0° direction. On the other hand, the "hard" layup gains strength in the 0° direction while decreasing its damage tolerance. Thus the designer must weigh the advantages and disadvantages of each layup candidate against the strength and damage tolerance requirements in the layup selection process. The prevailing rationale in selecting the 10/80/10 layup for the low velocity impact tests presented here was for the layup to provide relatively high damage tolerance while sacrificing a reasonable amount of 0° strength. It should be noted that a layup, such as 10/80/10, although specifying the proportions of the 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies, does not specify the stacking sequence of the individual plies. Since damage tolerance in composites, among many other parameters, is dependent on laminate thickness, five different thicknesses were selected for the specimens of this investigation. In terms of the

number of plies, the selected specimen thicknesses were 9, 26, 48, 74 and 96 plies. Trying to achieve precisely the 10/80/10 distribution in each of the five selected thicknesses was impossible. The final stacking sequences and corresponding layups deviating somewhat from the nominal 10/80/10 are shown in Table 1. The selected stacking sequence of the 26-and 74-ply laminates (D and F) made these laminates unsymmetrical about their midplane. Such slight deviation, however, had no significant consequence. The size of specimens was 7.78 cm x 25.40 cm and when subjected to impact they had ambient moisture content, i.e. the specimens were neither deliberately moisture preconditioned nor desiccated.

The panels for test specimens were cured in an autoclave under 689 kilo pascals pressure and 177°C temperature for two hours and without a post cure. The total cure cycle, including heat-up and cool-down ramps, took six hours. The panels were next ultrasonically inspected for quality and then cut into specimens using an eight-inch diameter diamond saw.

3.2. Equipment The specimens were impacted by a vertically falling 2.54 cm diameter steel hemispherical-end impactor while being sandwiched between a 2.54 cm thick steel base plate and a 1.90 cm thick aluminum cover plate, each having in its center a 12.7 cm square opening whose center coincided with that of the specimen. Clamps at the four corners held the plates and specimen tightly together (Ref. 2). The central opening in the top plate allowed the freely falling impactor to unobstructedly hit the specimen center while the base plate opening in conjunction with the four corner clamps allowed some flexure of the specimen. The boundary conditions of thusly supported specimen were neither fixed nor hinged but somewhere in between. The impact producing machine was a commercially available vertical drop tower with the capability to measure impactor velocity as well as contact load and impact energy histories during the impact event. The applied load was sensed by an accelerometer built into the impactor, electronically converted to common units and used to calculate the energy.

A special built-in device measured velocity of the impactor.

3.3 Procedures All testing was done at room temperature. Before proceeding with a series of tests for each of the five specimen thicknesses, velocity check was performed and the tup weight was determined. The velocity check consisted of calculating the velocity of the tup from its drop height ($V = \sqrt{2gh}$) and comparing it to that actually measured by the machine. Any difference between these two values was due to friction between the top harness and the vertical guide tubes. These tubes were cleaned until an insignificant difference between the two velocities was achieved. The maximum available impactor drop height of 1.1 m left the impactor weight as the only variable in arriving at the impact energy sufficient to produce the desired dent depths in the 9-, 26- and 48-ply specimens.

All specimens before being impacted were inspected by an ultrasonic through transmission NDI method and were found to be free of any significant manufacturing flaws. During the low velocity impact, the test specimens were supported in a fixture as described in paragraph 3.2 of this paper and Reference 2. All pertinent data, such as the drop height and velocity of the impactor, the impact load and energy histories, were recorded. A sample recording is shown in Figure 1. Next, the impacted specimens were inspected by the same NDI technique described above to determine the extent of the damaged area. The dent depths of impacted specimens were obtained by the shadow Moire technique. By this optical method, the topography of the depressed surface to be examined is described by dark fringes or contours representing loci of points equidistant from a medium plane. The contours, in an enlarged form, are projected on the screen of a monitor by the means of a CCD video camera that is pointed normal to the surface to be inspected. A setup of the equipment needed for a shadow Moire is illustrated in Figure 3. The contours are a combination of the parallel lines, etched in a flat glass plate placed in intimate contact with the depressed surface, and their shadows on this surface. The shadows are created by a light source placed at an angle to the normal of the surface to be examined. The

dent depth of a point on the depressed surface is calculated by multiplying the number of contours to the point by a predetermined factor that is a function of the density of the parallel lines on the glass plate and the angle between the direction of the light and the normal to the surface to be inspected. For a permanent record, the real-time picture of fringes on the monitor's screen can be either photographed or electronically saved in a computer. This procedure is described in detail in Reference 3.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Results in the form of average dent depths and damaged areas along with other pertinent test data are presented in Table 1. As can be seen there, the drop height for the 9-ply specimens is much smaller than those for the thicker specimens. The reason for this exception is that achieving the BVD (2.54 mm deep dent) in the relatively thin specimens (1.2002 mm) was impossible without the impactor penetrating the specimen. To avoid penetration, an impact was applied to cause a dent not to exceed the thickness of the specimen. With the tup weights set at 3.22, 4.20 and 7.01 kg, the drop heights had to be selected such as to meet the above criterion. This resulted in the average impactor velocity of 2.507 m/sec. as opposed to the intended 4.88 m/sec. The intended velocity and impact energy combination to cause a dent not to exceed the 9-ply specimen thickness could have been achieved if reducing the tup weight from its built-in minimum of about 3.2 kg to about 1.1 kg had been practical. The 26- and 48-ply specimens were impacted so as to cause approximately 2.54 mm deep dents. The impactor velocity associated with these tests averaged at 4.10 m/sec. The thickest specimens (74 and 96 plies) were impacted with about 136 joules energy and 3.88 m/sec impactor velocity each causing average dent depths of 0.826 mm for the 74- and 0.572 mm for the 96-ply specimens. It should be noted that the 136 joules impact energy is much smaller than that needed to produce 2.54 mm deep dent - about 217 and 319 joules for the 74- and 96-ply specimens respectively. However, the USAF damage tolerance criterion requires that the initial damage assumption be governed by the damage due to the lesser of

either 2.54 mm deep dent or 136 joules impact energy at 4.88 m/sec. Therefore, the tests reported here were conducted to investigate the damage tolerance of composites complying with the USAF damage tolerance requirements.

As can be seen from examining results in Table 1, approximately the same dent depth in a specimen of a given thickness can be achieved by about the same impact energy which is the product of tup weight and drop height. Hence there may be an infinite number of combinations of weight and height that will produce the same product. To avoid this ambiguity, the current practice is to fix the velocity. This fixes the drop height. The desired impact energy is then established by selecting the appropriate tup weight.

Another observation emerges from examining the damaged area values. Although approximate, they reflect a trend that makes some sense - for the same amount of impact energy, greater damaged areas are produced in the thicker specimens. In other words, thicker specimens, being stiffer, are more vulnerable to damage. This makes sense because the thinner specimens, being more flexible, dissipate a greater portion of the impact energy than the thicker, hence stiffer, specimens in flexural strain energy due to bending. Consequently, the thinner specimens have a smaller portion of the impact energy left for producing damage as compared with the thicker specimens.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Tests results support the use of impact indentation as a measure of initial damage suggested in the current USAF damage tolerance requirements for advanced composite structures. In addition, test observations indicate the need for dividing the laminate thickness range associated with indentation in two parts: 1. very thin laminates, say up to 20 plies or about 2.67 mm, and 2. thin laminates, approximately from 20 to 50 plies or up to about 6.67 mm. The need for separating the very thin laminates is based on the impossibility to produce a dent that is greater than the thickness of such laminates. The dent depth in these cases

would be limited to the thickness of the laminate while the dent depth in the neighboring thickness range (2.67 to 6.67 mm) would remain the current 2.54 mm.

A general suggestion, not necessarily based on test results presented here, is to develop either a standard low velocity impact tests or an analytic tool capable of "normalizing" data obtained in any two different low velocity impact tests. Satisfying this exigency would allow proper comparison and would significantly contribute to the expansion of valid impact data base.

REFERENCES

1. Air Force Guide Specification, AFGS-87221A, 8 June 1990.
2. NASA Reference Publication 1092, 1982.
3. Handbook on Experimental Mechanics, Society for Experimental Mechanics, Prentice-Hall, 1987.

BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCHES

ED DEMUTS

Out of his 37 years of experience in structural analysis and design, during the last 26 years Dr E. Demuts has been active in the development of technology for polymer matrix composite structures while being employed by the USAF in its Flight Dynamics Directorate at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio. The past ten years he has devoted to damage tolerance of composite structures, especially low velocity impact studies. He received his Bachelor of Civil Engineering (cum laude) and Master of Science degrees in 1955 and PhD degree in civil engineering in 1969, all from the Ohio State University. He is a member of ASCE, AIAA, SAMPE, American Society of Composites, American Academy of Mechanics, Sigma Xi, Tau Beta Pi and Chi Epsilon.

R. S. SANDHU

Dr R.S. Sandhu received his Bachelor of Arts Degree in Physics and Mathematics from Panjab University, Pakistan in 1944 and his Bachelor of Science Degree in Civil Engineering from Panjab University, India in 1950. He received his

Master of Engineering Degree in Structural Engineering from the University of Roorkee, India in 1959, and earned his Doctor of Philosophy Degree in Civil Engineering from the Ohio State University in 1968. Dr Sandhu joined the Flight Dynamics Laboratory in 1966 and is an aerospace engineer with Structures Division. He is a member of SEM, ASTM, AIAA, Sigma Xi and SAMPE.

TEMP (°C)	VELOC (m/sec)	IMPACT ENERGY (joules)	TIME		MAX LOAD (kN)	<u>ABSORBED ENERGY</u>	
			@ max ld (msec)	final (msec)		@ max ld (joules)	final (joules)
21.1	4.215	124.02	1.85	10.90	19.494	75.328	104.176

Figure 1. Impact Load and Energy History

Figure 2. Impact Energy for Use of Initial Damage Assumption

FIGURE 3. Shadow Moire Equipment Setup

TABLE 1 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

STACK SEQ *	# OF PLIES	CALCULATED SPECIMEN THICKNESS** (mm)	ACTUAL LAYUPS*** % OF 0/±45/90	WEIGHT OF IMPACTOR (kg)	# OF REPLIC	IMPACTOR DROP HEIGHT (cm)	VELOCITY CALC (m/sec)	VELOCITY MEAS (m/sec)	CALC (joules)	ENERGY MEAS (joules)	ABSORB (joules)	AVG DENT DEPTH (mm)	APPROX DAMAGE AREA (sq cm)
C	9	1.2002	22.2/66.7/11.1	3.22	4	39.83	2.80	2.77	12.57	12.39	9.80	1.702	
				4.20	5	30.48	2.44	2.42	12.57	12.32	10.30	1.321	
				7.01	1	18.19	1.89	1.87	12.50	12.26	9.46	1.194	
					10		AVE	2.51		12.34	10.02	1.461	6.45
D	26	3.4671	11.5/77.0/11.5	6.99	4	71.12	3.73	3.72	48.78	48.21	39.86	1.956	
				4.80	3	103.56	4.51	4.48	48.78	48.28	39.96	2.489	
					7		AVE	4.05		48.24	39.90	2.184	19.35
E	48	6.4008	12.5/75/12.5	13.95	4	91.44	4.23	4.22	125.11	124.17	102.09	3.175	
				24.22	4	52.35	3.20	3.19	124.33	123.47	93.21	3.251	
					8		AVE	3.70		123.82	97.65	3.213	103.23
F	74	9.8679	12.2/75.6/12.2	13.95	4	100.20	4.43	4.42	137.10	136.46	70.98	0.787	
				24.22	4	57.35	3.35	3.34	136.21	135.09	61.11	0.864	
					8		AVE	3.88		135.78	66.04	0.826	116.13
G	96	12.8016	12.5/75.0/12.5	13.95	4	100.20	4.43	4.42	137.10	136.40	58.75	0.635	
				24.22	4	57.35	3.35	3.34	136.21	135.30	49.77	0.508	
					8		AVE	3.88		135.85	54.26	0.572	116.13

* STACKING SEQUENCES

- C: (±45/0/45/90/45/0/-45/45)
- D: (±45/0/±45₂/90/±45₂/0/90/-45/45/-45/45/90/-45/45/-45/45/0/-45/45)
- E: (±45/0/±45₂/90)_{3S}
- F: (±45/0/±45₂/90)₄/±45₂/0/90/-45/45/-45/45/(90/-45/45/-45/45/0/-45/45)₄
- G: (±45/0/±45₂/90)_{6S}

TEST TEMPERATURE: ROOM TEMPERATURE (RT)
 MOISTURE CONDITION OF SPECIMENS: AMBIENT
 ** NOMINAL PLY THICKNESS: 0.13335 mm
 *** NOMINAL LAYUP: 10/80/10